

TANGENT

REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES (INCLUDING COOPERATION WITH OTHER PROJECTS). FIRST RELEASE.

D8.3

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<https://www.linkedin.com/company/tangent-project/>

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhz4kwEm_sTHj7fE4zXToA

For further information please visit <http://www.tangent-h2020.eu/>

Executive summary

D8.3 report on dissemination activities, which includes cooperation with other projects and reviews the progress achieved in the first 18 months of the TANGENT project. First, it goes over the physical and digital project identity, which includes the project leaflet, roll-up banner, newsletters, website and social media channels. Then, the report breakdowns the publications, events and conferences which showcased the project's ambitions, results and findings. As regards collaborations with external partners, it describes the activities of the 4FRONT Cluster (sister projects) as well as the TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum. Finally, the report gives an overview of the upcoming dissemination activities planned for the second part of the project.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Full Name
AB	Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
TRA	Transport Research Arena
TRB	Transportation Research Board
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse.
AB	Advisory Board
WS	Workshop

1 Introduction

1.1 Objectives and intended audience

Since the beginning of the project the TANGENT consortium has paid a great attention to the definition and implementation of a sound dissemination strategy for the TANGENT project. A first Dissemination and Communication Plan (Deliverable 8.1.) was submitted in December 2021, presenting the dissemination activities planned, as well as the branding of the project, identification of the dissemination material, channels and communications measures to be undertaken throughout the lifetime of the project. The dissemination plan continuously runs throughout the project's lifetime.

- It is comprehensive as it relates to the activities of all work packages (WP).
- It is flexible as it shall be adapted according to the projects' findings and partners' needs.

The dissemination activities started at very early stages, using a wide range of dissemination channels and materials, in order to stimulate interest from all stakeholders and interested parties.

The Dissemination Plan is intended to be a living document, since, at this stage in the project lifetime, the dissemination main focus has now shifted from raising awareness amongst all stakeholders and interested parties about the project's existence and activities to supporting growing exploitation activities with users able to test and validate the results as well as with potential customers, i.e. interested public or private organisations.

The present document covers the dissemination activities carried out from September 2021 to February 2023 (M1 to M18 of the project). The report also outlines the planned dissemination activities for the upcoming period.

2 Physical Project Identity

TANGENT’s communication and dissemination activities, as well as its cooperation with other initiatives, are based on a strong digital and physical presence. The latter includes printed material, like leaflets and banners, which are essential to reach various target audiences.

2.1 Project leaflet

A high-quality project **leaflet** was produced in the early phases of the project (December 2021) to present TANGENT. It is both available for download on the website and it was printed. The leaflet aims to inform a wide audience about the project’s objectives, approach, pilot cities and consortium. It was brought to events and conferences (TRA, POLIS Conference, TRB, etc.) for distribution by all project partners. [Link to leaflet.](#)

Figure 1: TANGENT Leaflet

Figure 2 : TANGENT Survey Leaflet for TRA conference

In addition, a leaflet was created and printed for the TRA conference to gather responses for the WP3 survey on travellers’ daily travel patterns in Athens, Lisbon, Rennes and Manchester.

Next steps

A leaflet for the 4Front Consortium will be designed and delivered by POLIS in May 2023, in time for the ITS Europe Congress, to present the cluster of sister projects.

Other leaflets, for specific activities and tasks, will be created. This could be the case, for example, to promote activities in pilots, surveys, and publications.

2.2 Roll-up banner

To promote TANGENT at key events around Europe, a **roll-up banner** was produced to showcase the project’s logo, key messages, case study cities, and website. The banner was presented at Connecting Europe Days, TRA conference, POLIS annual conference, and more.

Figure 3: Roll up banner at events (left: TRA conference, November 2022; right: Connecting Europe Days, June 2022)

3 Digital Project Identity

3.1 Newsletters

TANGENT published three newsletters which covered the project’s activities, events, deliverables, and progress on the use cases. The articles were co-written by POLIS and relevant consortium members, including ID4CAR, NTUA and DEUSTO. The TANGENT newsletter currently has 40 subscribers.

The first newsletter featured opening words from the project coordinator (Leire Serrano), updates and pictures of in-person workshops in the use cases, and updates on the creation of the Advisory Board.

The second newsletter went over the project’s results in its first year, the consortium meeting in Bilbao (September 2022), the achievement of the cities, an interview of NTUA’s work in the project, described three deliverables, the upcoming events TANGENT was going to participate in, and gave updates on the sister projects.

The third newsletter promoted the cooperative decision-making survey of WP5, presented the members of the Advisory Board and the kick, showcased events TANGENT participated in and showcased two key deliverables through a short description (D1.4 and D2.2).

The newsletters are available on the [website](#).

Figure 4: TANGENT first, second and third newsletters

3.2 Website

TANGENT’s **website** is a key platform for the project’s visibility. Since its launch, 12 original articles were posted to provide an overview on the research deliverables, workshops and in-person meetings, project milestones, participation in international events and more (Figure 5).

In addition, two exclusive interviews with the pilots of Greater Manchester (Hannah Tune) in May 2022 and Athens through NTUA (Eleni Mantouka) in September 2022 were conducted and posted on the platform (Figure 6). Two other interviews, Rennes and Lisbon, are planned for the second half of the project.

On average, per month, the website has around 200 unique users. The website domain name is www.tangent-h2020.eu and in line with the overview presented in “D8.2 Website and Social Networks Profiles” delivered in December 2021.

Figure 5: TANGENT Website's News Section

CITY SPOTLIGHT: INTERVIEW WITH ELENI MANTOUKA, NTUA

In September, we asked Dr [Eleni Mantouka](#) – *Civil & Transportation Engineer and Senior Researcher at the School of Civil Engineering of the National Technical University of Athens* – to tell us more about the [Athens](#) virtual case study.

What are the goals of the Athens virtual pilot in TANGENT?

Athens has a very old road network which is often very congested. In order to relief congestion and mitigate air pollution, the priority for the city is to push for public transport use, render space for pedestrians and promote green mobility. Therefore, we expect that the TANGENT solutions will help to reduce congestion in the city and improve air quality. Giving light to the same performance indicators within TANGENT, we expect to study the impacts of introducing new mobility services, such as connected and automated vehicles.

In TANGENT, Athens has a specific status: it is a virtual case study. What exactly is a virtual case study? Do you work with the municipality of Athens?

A virtual case study refers to a simulation-based representation of the road network with all its specifications together with its supply and demand for movement in the city. The main advantage of the virtual study, which incorporates a very well calibrated microscopic model for the city of Athens, is that it gives the opportunity to test several scenarios including the introduction of new mobility services, the effect of several types of incidents, as well as the impact of new traffic management strategies. Having this very powerful tool, we are able to estimate specific KPIs based on which we can evaluate the different solutions for the city.

NTUA as a university is very interested in the research perspective of how the Athens transport network may evolve in the future and, within this context, several research projects have been formed with the cooperation of both the Municipality of Athens and the Region of Attica.

How do you work with the other TANGENT cities?

The TANGENT consortium has established great collaborations between the partners for the development of TANGENT services, where the cities' priorities have been identified and described in detail. However, at the moment, we do not work directly with the other cities. We expect that as the project evolves the rest of the cities may take advantage of our test bed to get some insights on future mobility solutions that cannot be tested in other cities' real pilots, like for example connected and automated vehicles.

Figure 6: City Spotlight, example of an interview with a TANGENT city

3.3 Social Media Channels

The TANGENT [Twitter page](#) and [LinkedIn page](#) have been available and active since the start of the project. They follow a defined graphic charter and tone, laid out in D8.1.

In addition to regular updates and photographs, visuals were designed by POLIS to increase the appeal of the channels. To give an example, to promote the first three research deliverables and [an article](#) on their key findings published on the TANGENT's website, three visuals were created for LinkedIn and

Twitter. The goal was to create visibility and interest on TANGENT’s outputs for the wider public and particularly researchers.

Figure 7: Social Media Visuals for Twitter and LinkedIn

	Twitter	LinkedIn	Total
Followers	69	179	248
Original Posts (TANGENT account)	42	33	75
Consortium members channels posts on TANGENT	9	16	25
Sister projects posts on 4FRONT	8	4	12

Table 1: Overview of Twitter and LinkedIn engagement and posts

4 Publications

4.1 Press releases, the media and magazines

Press releases are important means to establish the project’s identity. In the first half of the project, there have been no press releases in the mass media due to the launch of the activities. However, a strong emphasis was put on getting a press release on the consortium’s own websites. Therefore, POLIS, ID4MOBILITY, DEUSTO and Rupprecht Consult posted a press release on their website to kick off of the project in 2021.

There will be a strong emphasis on sharing findings from the project in the **mass media** in the second half of the project, particularly in the pilot cities where partners will be encouraged to communicate with the local press to inform their end users and citizens about their progress.

Figure 8: TANGENT press release on the POLIS and ID4MOBILITY websites

Links to other press releases follow:

[POLIS](#)

[ID4MOBILITY](#)

[Deusto](#)

[Rupprecht Consult](#)

In addition, TANGENT was featured in a **magazine** in 2022, POLIS’ Cities in Motion, in an article on traffic management and the potential environmental, social and safety benefits of thinking beyond motorized traffic. The “Traffic Management 101” article, co-written by Juliette Thijs and Dagmara Wrzesińska (POLIS), is available at the following link (p. 85-87): [Cities in motion - POLIS Network](#)

Figure 9: TANGENT article in "Cities in Motion" magazine

4.2 Scientific Publications

TANGENT aims to publish at least 8 articles and scientific papers in specialised media, magazines, and journals. These are means to target transport professionals and urban mobility practitioners.

TANGENT will contribute to the FAIR principles ('findability', 'accessibility', 'interoperability' and 'reusability') of open research through open peer-reviewed publications. Five articles have been published. However, it is foreseen that many more will be made available during the second half of the project's implementation, when the pilot activities and the most relevant deliverables will be ready.

DATE	TITLE OF PERIODICAL / SERIES	TITLE OF ITEM/ARTICLE	AUTHOR(S)
14-17/11/22	Transport Research Arena TRA Lisbon 2022	Travel Behavior Shifts under Extreme System-Level Disruptions	Christina Gasparinatu, Eleni Mantouka, Eleni Vlahogianni, Antonio David Masegosa, Leire Serrano
27/01/22	hEART Symposium 2022	Investigating the acceptance and willingness-to-pay of an urban pricing scheme: The case of Athens	Christina Gasparinatu, Eleni Mantouka, Eleni Vlahogianni, John Golias
21/01/22		Efficient Traffic Demand Forecasting Using a Meaningful Representation With Social Multiplex Networks and Community Detection	Eleftheria Karakitsou, Panagiotis Fafoutellis, Eleni I. Vlahogianni

DATE	TITLE OF PERIODICAL / SERIES	TITLE OF ITEM/ARTICLE	AUTHOR(S)
09/01/23	TRB Annual Meeting 2023	A Multi-level Approach to Link Smooth Driving with Safe Driver Behavior	Eleni Mantouka, Panagiotis Fafoutellis, Dimitrios Tselentis, Eleonora Papadimitriou, Eleni Vlahogianni, George Yannis
11/01/23		Multimodal Traffic Demand Prediction Using a Community Detection Framework on Social Multiplex Networks	Panagiotis Fafoutellis, Eleftheria Karakitsou, Eleni I. Vlahogianni

Table 2: List of Scientific Publications

5 Events and Conferences

TANGENT participated in a range of events and conferences to increase visibility of the project, as well as disseminate the results, findings and key outputs. A comprehensive list of these are presented below.

TITLE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	DATE	LOCATION	DISS. LEVEL	PARTNER ATTENDING	TANGENT PROMOTION
hEART Symposium https://heart2022.com/about-leuven/	KU Leuven and the University of Luxembourg	1/6/2022	Leuven	European	NTUA	presentation
The Mobility Data Platform Coordination Organisation https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rjndSn8uY2U	NAPCORE	18/2/2022	online	European	A-to-Be	Attendance for looking collaboration opportunities FOR TANGENT (using PT NAPs)
RUDI project - portal for data webinar	ID4CAR	22/2/2022	online	Local	Training	other
FastTrack Capacity Building Week https://fasttrackmobility.eu/events?c=search&uid=ycxXqgDN Agenda available here: https://fasttrackmobility.eu/fileadmin/user_upload/News_Events/CBW2_programme.pdf	Fast Track project	31/3/2022	online	European	Deusto	presentation
GIRO Workshop 2022 - Knowledge graphs for interoperability in the transportation domain https://giro.cefriel.it/	CEFRIEL	5/3/2022	online	Global	CEFRIEL	presentation
4FRONT: Developing traffic and network management of the future	4FRONT (cluster of sister projects)	14/6/2022	online	European	Deusto	Presentation & organisation of the event
Connecting Europe Days connectingeuropedays.europa.eu	European Commission	28/6/2022	Lyon	European	POLIS	Presentation + exhibition stand
Fourth International Workshop On Semantics And The Web For Transport	CEFRIEL	13/9/2022	Wien	Global	CEFRIEL	presentation

TITLE OF EVENT	ORGANISER	DATE	LOCATION	DISS. LEVEL	PARTNER ATTENDING	TANGENT PROMOTION
(https://sem4tra2022.linkedindata.es/)						
Urban Mobility Days https://www.eumd.org/en	Eltis/ European Commission	20- 22/09/2022	Brno	European	Rupprecht Consult	stand
					Deusto	presentation
ITS UK Summit https://its-uk.org.uk/	ITS UK	13/10/22	Milton Keynes	National	TFGM	Attendance for looking collaboration opportunities for TANGENT (accessing PT NAPs).
TRA 2022 https://traconference.eu/	Transport Research Board (supported by EC)	14/11/2022	Lisbon	European	Deusto	Common invited session with 4FRONT (presentation & panel discussion) Project stand
Transport Technology Forum https://tff.uk.net/	Department for Transport	15/11/22	Manchester	National	TfGM	Presentation from Transport Commissioner on general TfGM activity including TANGENT
POLIS Conference 2022	POLIS	30/11/2022	Brussels	European	POLIS, ID4CAR	Exhibition stand
TRB 2023 https://www.trb.org/AnnualMeeting/AnnualMeeting.aspx	Transport Research Board	8- 12/01/2023	Washington	Global	NTUA	Academic poster stand

Table 3: Database of TANGENT participation in conferences and events

Additionally, TANGENT has organised various workshops with stakeholders in order to (a) define the user needs and TANGENT system requirements, (b) identify multi-actor cooperation models in the transport network management, in the framework of WP1. 3 workshops have been organised per Case Study, online and onsite. In the workshops different stakeholders of the transport network relevant for each case study participated. The full detail of the workshops is covered in deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D1.3. In Table 6 the number of participants per workshop for the different case studies is indicated.

6 Clustering activities with other EU projects

TANGENT is related to different EU funded projects in the traffic management domain. From the beginning a collaboration was established with the sister projects funded under the same call topic, “MG-2-11-2020 - Network and traffic management for future mobility”¹, this being: DIT4TRAM², FRONTIER³ and ORCHESTRA⁴, the cluster of projects is called 4FRONT cluster.

The 4FRONT cluster had various audio meetings to look for synergies among the projects, and identifying collaboration opportunities, the meeting dates are shown in the next table.

	Dates
4FRONT cluster audio meetings	25/01/2022
	14/06/2022
	27/10/2022
	10/11/2022

Table 4: 4FRONT cluster audio meetings

So far, the projects have collaborated in various events, further details follow:

TRA conference 2022. Lisbon, November 2022

At the TRA conference 2022, the 4FRONT cluster together with the European Commission and HARMONY project⁵, organised an invited session entitled “A snapshot to the traffic management of the future”⁶. The session examined the future of network and traffic management, and the ways it will shape cities. The session explored how to tackle new technological, societal, operational, business and governance challenges and opportunities. The projects presented the progress covering System engineering architecture, Resilience, Trustworthiness, Data sharing, Governance, User behaviour and acceptance, multimodality, upscaling etc. to implement the network and traffic management of the future. DEUSTO represented the project in the session. Next the details about the session follow:

	TRA conference 2022
Moderator	Thiago Tavares, CINEA (European Commission)
Organisers	Fanny Breuil, EURECAT / FRONTIER Runar Søråsen, ITS Norway / ORCHESTRA

¹ https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_MG-2-11-2020

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/953783>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955317>

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/953618>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/815269/es>

⁶ <https://traconference.eu/invited-sessions/monday/>

TRA conference 2022	
	<p>Leire Serrano, DeustoTech/ TANGENT</p> <p>Serge Hoogendoorn, Professor Smart Urban Mobility, TU Delft / DIT4TRAM</p> <p>Maria Kamargianni, UCL UK / HARMONY</p>
Speakers	<p>Akrivi Kiousi, FRONTIER and Netcompany Intrasoft</p> <p>Runar Søråsen, ORCHESTRA/ ITS Norway</p> <p>Antonio Masegosa, TANGENT/ DeustoTech</p> <p>Leire Serrano, TANGENT/ DeustoTech</p> <p>Ludovic Leclercq, DIT4TRAM/ University Eiffel</p> <p>Vicent Pastor, Enide/ HARMONY</p>

Table 5: Details about the invited session on “A snapshot to the traffic management of the future”

Figure 10: Invited session at the TRA conference

Additionally, TANGENT and ORCHESTRA shared a stand at the conference for promoting the results obtained so far in the projects. Several partners of TANGENT participated: DEUSTO, CEFRIEL, NTUA, CARRIS and A-to-Be.

Figure 11: TANGENT partners at the stand at the TRA conference

POLIS conference. Brussels, November 2022

TANGENT project was present at the POLIS conference 2022 in Brussels. For two days the project results were showcased in an exhibition stand shared with other projects: DIT4TRAM and MobiDataLab⁷. Representatives from POLIS and ID4CAR were present at the booth.

Figure 12: TANGENT stand at POLIS conference

Connecting Europe Days Lyon, 28-30 June 2022

The 4FRONT projects shared an exhibitor stand during 2 days at the Connecting Europe Days in Lyon for promoting the projects. In addition, TANGENT was featured at the French Automotive & Mobility Network exhibitor stand, thanks to the involvement of ID4CAR and Rennes Metropole in the project.

Additionally, the TANGENT project was presented in a pitch session devoted to innovation projects.

⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006879/es>

Figure 13: Representatives of 4FRONT cluster of projects at the Connecting Europe Days Lyon

Figure 14: Pitch of TANGENT project

Furthermore, **TANGENT** and **ORCHESTRA** are in contact for identifying further liaisons between both projects. These held an audio on the 29th of November 2022 and 21st of February 2023, where both projects were presented including the technical aspects. One of the areas of common interest are the traffic cooperation models.

The 24th of February 2023 the **final conference of HARMONY project** will be held. TANGENT will be represented in the poster session by AIMSUN. Further information available here: <https://harmony-h2020.eu/final-conference-harmonyh2020/>

7 TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum

The **TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum** were established in February 2023 and are led by Rupprecht Consult under WP1 activity 1.4. On the one hand, the Advisory Board (AB) comprises of a dozen stakeholders including researchers, local authorities, and the industry and transport operators which were selected by Rupprecht Consult, Deusto and POLIS. The Advisory Board is made of members who signed Letters of Interest during the proposal phase as well as stakeholders who responded to call for stakeholders launched by POLIS in the summer 2022 and stakeholders from the network of DEUSTO; POLIS and Rupprecht Consult. The AB will overlook the project from an external, independent perspective providing strategic input, guidance and support to the project on an annual basis. As a strategic body, they will meet three times in the project lifetime. On the other hand, the TANGENT Forum is a wider, but exclusive, group of professionals in the mobility sector which will have a front row seat on the project activities, events and results. Forum members will serve to validate outcomes and outputs of the project and maximise the take up of its results and products. This will be facilitated on a dedicated platform on the Mobility Academy, shared with the Advisory Board members.

The TANGENT Forum space will include:

- A TANGENT Cities page where members can learn more about the four pilot cities' goals and vision in the implementation of TANGENT tools and services (Athens, Greater Manchester, Lisbon and Rennes)
- A Discussion Forum where they will be able to interact and network with other professionals who share an interest in traffic management and other mobility challenges.
- TANGENT webinars, presenting key project results and the tools developed, and collecting feedback from key stakeholders. They will have access to extra materials used during these webinars. These include;
 - Webinar 1: Introduction to Network and Traffic Management
 - Webinar 2: Real-time traffic modelling and forecasting tools
 - Webinar 3: Transport Network optimisation and arbitration models
 - Webinar 4: Integrated tool for Cooperative Traffic Management and results of case study I implementation.

The AB kick-off took place on the 10th of February 2023 through an interactive 1h30 session where the project's objectives were presented and the AB members took part in interactive Miro board exercises.

Figure 15: AB Kick off meeting

8 Planning of next dissemination activities

8.1 Events, conferences and publications

This year, the project has already planned a series of **events and conferences** it will participate in to do presentations, present papers and/or exhibit the project. These include, but are not limited to, the following events:

- HARMONY Final Conference, April 2023.
- ITS Europe conference in Lisbon (Portugal), May 2023.
- IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC) in Bilbao (Spain), September 2023.
- POLIS Annual Conference 2023.
- A 4Front cluster webinar on data governance, June 2023.
- TANGENT Forum meets in person once, side by side.

At the end of the project, there will also be two different **publications** on its key exploitable outcomes will be delivered, which will be tailored to the wide diversity of target groups.

- A final booklet summarising the main project results, outputs, and tools in an easy to read and concise format. This will be presented as a user-friendly brochure (+/- 12 pages, A4 format).
- The second will be a policy document targeted at public authorities that describes the link between multi-modal network management and policy and makes recommendations on how multimodal network management can be integrated into policy and planning processes. This will be presented as a more comprehensive and detailed brochure (approx. 28/32 pages, A4 format).

8.2 Clustering with 4FRONT and other initiatives

Mentioned above, TANGENT consortium has already planned various activities with other EU projects:

- ITS Europe conference in Lisbon (Portugal), May 2023. A proposal of a special session has been submitted in collaboration with 4FRONT cluster.
- IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC) in Bilbao (Spain), September 2023. A proposal of a special session has been submitted in collaboration among University of Deusto, Josef Stefan Institute⁸ and National technical University of Athens (NTUA)⁹. These entities are involved in various EU projects on the domain of traffic management, such as TANGENT, CONDUCTOR and DIT4TRAM.
- A webinar on data governance will be organised in June 2023, in cooperation with 4FRONT cluster.

8.3 TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum

The TANGENT Advisory Board and Forum activities will take place in the second half of the project. In addition to the webinars stated in Section 7, a Policy Recommendations Workshop will be held at the end of the project to discuss policy implications and derive key recommendations and lessons learned from TANGENT's results and outputs. The workshop will be open to the public, but a stronger focus will be put on the AB.

⁸ <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/JSI>

⁹ <https://www.ntua.gr/en/>

As part of the TANGENT Forum activities, a discussion forum will contribute to the dissemination and uptake of TANGENT results.

8.4 Other planned activities

As the project progresses, it is foreseen to elaborate more advanced audio-visual contents, particularly for the use case studies. One short promotional video is foreseen in the second half of the project to present an overview of the four cities and the work they are achieving within TANGENT. A second video may be produced at the end of the project to showcase its achievements and findings.

9 Conclusions

In the first half of the project, TANGENT’s communication, dissemination and exploitation activities have been successful in reaching the objectives of the “D8.1 Dissemination and communication plan” developed in month three.

A strong emphasis was put on ensuring TANGENT had a recognizable identity and a thorough visibility. This was achieved through the creation of a brand identity, regular updates of activities on the project’s website and social media channels, participation in European and international conferences and events, and through articles in academic publications. In the last 18 months, TANGENT has fostered an environment of strong cooperation with its sister projects (4FRONT) through regular calls to strategically align and by co-participating in sessions at events.

In the second half of the project, TANGENT will continue to focus on these activities. In addition, the project consortium will involve its AB and Forum in communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The project will also focus more strongly on exploitation, with a higher degree of visibility in the mass media and key events.

Communication tools	KPIs	Level of performance DoA	Level of performance M1-M18	Comment
Project website	No. of visits/ No. of followers	[800-1000/ year]/ [300/ year]	Information not available	Currently the information is not available, we will update in the next release of dissemination plan (D8.7)
Press releases in mass media	No. publications in the media	> 8/ project	1	Cities in Motion magazine A stronger focus will be put in the second half of the project to communicate the project’s activities and results. There will be a high interest from the media once the pilot’s have progressed, the tool is out, and key outputs have been published.
Social media channels	Followers/ tweets and posts	+450 followers/ 150 posts	Twitter: 71 followers. LinkedIn:181 followers. TOTAL of followers: 252 Posts: 78	Indicator reached, no comment
Promotional material	No. videos/ No. material designs	[1/ year]/ [3/ project]	2/3	A project leaflet and roll-up banner were finalised, printed and showcased at events. A video will be produced in the second half of the project.

Communication tools	KPIs	Level of performance DoA	Level of performance M1-M18	Comment
Events	No. of presentations	[4-6/ year]/ [15/project]	9 presentations	Presentations are already planned in the second half of the project. The indicator will be easily achieved.
Workshops/ events	No. of participants	>20 attendees/ workshop/ > 100/ project (including final event)	<p>Number of participants in the workshops organised in WP1 (excluding TANGENT partners). Per Case Study:</p> <p>Total no. of participants (WS 1, WS 2, WS 3)</p> <p>Rennes: 24 (10, 7, 7)</p> <p>Lisbon: 26 (11, 9, 6)</p> <p>Manchester: 31 (21, 5, 5)</p>	

Table 6: TANGENT's Key Performance Indicators on dissemination activities

10 References

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